

Education Quarterly Reviews

Srisopha, K. (2022). Factors Affecting Students' Achievement in English Language Learning at Thailand National Sports University of Central Region. *Education Quarterly Reviews*, 5(2), 59-66.

ISSN 2621-5799

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1993.05.02.468

The online version of this article can be found at:
<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

The *Education Quarterly Reviews* is an Open Access publication. It may be read, copied, and distributed free of charge according to the conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

The Asian Institute of Research *Education Quarterly Reviews* is a peer-reviewed International Journal. The journal covers scholarly articles in the fields of education, linguistics, literature, educational theory, research, and methodologies, curriculum, elementary and secondary education, higher education, foreign language education, teaching and learning, teacher education, education of special groups, and other fields of study related to education. As the journal is Open Access, it ensures high visibility and the increase of citations for all research articles published. The *Education Quarterly Reviews* aims to facilitate scholarly work on recent theoretical and practical aspects of education.

ASIAN INSTITUTE OF RESEARCH
Connecting Scholars Worldwide

Factors Affecting Students' Achievement in English Language Learning at Thailand National Sports University of Central Region

Kwanklao Srisopha¹

¹ Thailand National Sports University Chon Buri Campus. Email: ajkwan.s@gmail.com

Abstract

The objectives of this research were 1) to study the relationship between student factors, English language instructor factors, and environment factors with students' achievement in English language learning and 2) to develop equations to forecast factors affecting students' achievement in English language learning. The population used in this research was 415 students of Thailand National Sports University of Central Region enrolled in the English for Communication Course in the second semester of the academic year 2019. The sample size was determined using the Krejcie & Morgan table. A sample of 200 was obtained and a simple random sampling method was used based on the proportion of the population on each of the five campuses. The research instrument was a five-rating scale questionnaire comprising items on student factors, English language instructor factors and environment factors, with a reliability of the whole questionnaire of 0.973. The statistics used in the data analysis were fundamental statistics, Pearson correlation analysis, and stepwise multiple regression analysis. The major findings indicated that there were four factors affecting students' achievement in English language learning with statistical significance at the .01 level namely, attitude variables towards learning English language course (X_1), instruction management variable (X_4), student availability variable (X_2), and classroom environment variable (X_7). The four factors could jointly explain the variance of students' achievement in English language learning by 52.50% and could be used to forecast students' achievement in English language learning in the form of raw scores and standard scores as follows:

$$Y' = 1.125 + .320 X_1 + .139 X_4 + .124 X_2 + .096 X_7$$

$$Z' = .375 z_1 + .165 z_4 + .145 z_2 + .128 z_7$$

Keywords: Achievement in English Language Learning, Thailand National Sports University of Central Region

1. Introduction

His Majesty King Maha Vajiralongkorn Bodindradebayavarangkun is graciously pleased to proclaim that it is expedient to revise the law on institutions of physical education, it is graciously enacted by the King, by and with the advice and consent of the National Legislative Assembly acting as the National Assembly. This Act is called "The National Sports University Act, 2019" announced in the Government Gazette on 22 May 2019 and stipulates the powers and duties in Section 8 that the University shall be an academic and professional educational institution in the field of sports with the objectives of providing education, promoting academics and professions, teaching,

researching and develop academic and professional services to society, nurturing arts and culture by focusing on creating knowledge in sports, physical education, health promotion, sports science, sports management, business and sports industry and related disciplines, as well as being a source of building and developing personnel in the field of sports in the country.

The elevation of the university status has made the role of sport and related disciplines more distinctive, diverse and international, and thus there is a need to intensively improve students' English proficiency. This is in line with the policy and goals of the Office of the Higher Education Commission that Thai graduates' English proficiency should be on par with graduates in ASEAN Member States (Office of the Higher Education Commission, 2010) in accordance with the ASEAN Charter, Article 34, "The working language of ASEAN shall be English" and in accordance with the policy of raising English language standards in higher education institutions according to the announcement of the Commission on Higher Education, which stipulates 4 issues as follows: 1) To have higher education institutions formulate policies and goals for raising English language standards in higher education institutions in all programs and at all levels of education to be a guideline to develop students' English proficiency skills to become graduates who are equipped with academic, professional and English communication skills at a working knowledge level. 2) Have higher education institutions prepare a plan to implement policies and goals with clear indicators and assessments. 3) Institutions of higher education shall consider improving the teaching and learning management in English course with an aim to achieve the goals set. 4) Higher education institutions shall consider organizing extracurricular activities, processes, media and/or environments that will provide opportunities and enhance motivation for students to develop their English language skills on their own; and 5) Institutions of higher education shall arrange for all students to test their English language proficiency in accordance with the Higher Education Standards Test created by the institution or which it deems appropriate to use to measure English Proficiency, which can be compared with Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR) or another standard to determine the level of competence of each student.

The Institute of Physical Education has always given importance to the development of English language skills and proficiency, as can be seen from the designation of English course as a compulsory course in the foreign language group and in the Institute of Physical Education Strategic Plan B.E. 2007-2013 that has set a goal of organizing activities to promote and develop the use of English for students to be able to use English both in study and in work. Especially now that when it has been upgraded to the National Sports University, the development of English language proficiency for students is even more important because after graduating graduates must be able to use English for work; just like Wiley and Wrigley (1987) said, English is important to students and individuals moving to work. In particular, in line with the National Sports University Act, Article 9 (3), which states that "strengthening the network of cooperation in education and sports with communities, government agencies, private sector, educational institutions and international sports organizations."

As English is not the main language of Thailand, learning English for Thai people must be learned from language learning in educational institutions. This is in line with the Willkins concept of language learning (Willkins, 1974), which states that language learning is divided into two types: 1) language acquisition and 2) language learning. The management of English language teaching according to the curriculum of the National Sports University has arranged for students to study English for Communication Course Code 051057 as a compulsory course with the objective of enabling learners to be able to listen, speak, read and write English for basic communication in various situations. Including to enable learners to be able to apply knowledge and English skills appropriately in daily life by requiring students to study content according to the course descriptions as follows; "English sentence patterns and structures and practicing listening, speaking, reading, writing in daily life about greeting and farewell, introducing yourself and others, describing the nature of things and people, giving advice or giving suggestions, inquiries and information about exercise and sports, time, weather conditions, directions, prices" Therefore, if the student's learning achievement in English for communication is at a good or very good level, students will be able to use English as an important tool for communication, education, pursuit of knowledge, and sports competitions. International, occupational, cultural understanding in a global context and awareness of cultural diversity and global social perspectives which will bring friendship and cooperation with other countries, help develop students to have a better understanding of themselves and others. In addition, the study of factors affecting students'

achievement in English language learning will be of great benefit in order to use the research findings to plan for curricular development and teaching and learning to increase English language course achievement.

2. Conceptual framework

From the study of concepts and theories related to factors affecting learning achievement from both Thai and foreign academics such as Bloom (Benjamin S. Bloom, 1976), stating that two important factors determined a student's school record, namely: a student's academic history, and quality of instructional management of teachers. This was consistent with Cremer's (1994) concept that the effectiveness of instruction derived from instructional management by a teacher. This was consistent with the findings of Chatkaew Powwiset and Wanwipha Chatuchai (2013), Paiboon Sukwijit (2010), Aimachara Khotkaew et al. (2011), Nuchanrat Vorayossri (2001), stating that factors affecting language learning achievement consisted of learners, teachers, and classroom teaching environment and social context. Therefore, the research conceptual framework was developed by the researcher using the foresaid concept as follows:

3. Research objectives

1. To study the relationship between student factors, English language instructor factors, and environment factors with students' achievement in English language learning at Thailand National Sports University of Central Region.
2. To create forecast equations for factors affecting students' achievement in English language learning at Thailand National Sports University of Central Region.

4. Research Hypothesis

There is at least one factor that can predict students' achievement in English language learning at Thailand National Sports University of Central Region.

5. Scope of research

The subjects used in this research study were English for Communication Course, course code NS 051057 according to the curriculum of the National Sports University, 2019.

6. Population and sample

The population and sample used in this research were: 415 students of the Thailand National Sports University of Central Region, consisting of 5 campuses including Bangkok Campus, Chonburi Campus, Samut Sakhon Campus, Suphanburi Campus, and Angthong Campus who registered for the English for Communication course in the second semester of the academic year 2019. The sample size was determined using the Krejcie and Morgan table. A sample number of 200 was obtained and a simple random sampling method was used from the students of the Thailand National Sports University of Central Region's five campuses according to the proportion of the population on each campus.

7. Variables studied

The independent variables were factors affecting students' achievement in English language learning at Thailand National Sports University of Central Region, consisting of the following variables:

8. Student factors

1. Attitude towards learning English (X_1).
2. Readiness of students (X_2)
3. Study motivation (X_3)

9. English language instructor factors

1. Learning management (X_4).
2. Instructor's personality (X_5).
3. Students' opinions acceptance (X_6).

10. Environment factors

1. Classroom environment (X_7).
2. Family education support (X_8).

The dependent variables were the learning achievement of English for Communication course, course code NS 051057 of students of the Thailand National Sports University of Central Region, academic year 2019.

11. Methods of research

1. Study the concepts, theories and research related to factors affecting Achievement in English language learning.
2. Create a questionnaire on factors affecting learning achievement in English, 1 questionnaire consisted of 82 questions.
3. The questionnaire was sent to 3 experts for analysis and examination to determine the content validity and appropriateness of language use, and then select the questions with an index of congruence (IOC: Index of congruence) starting from 0.6 or higher, 75 items.
4. The pre-selected questionnaires were tested by asking non-sample students to determine their reliability. The confidence value of the whole questionnaire was 0.934.
5. Coordinate with the research office of the Thailand National Sports University of Central Region in all 5 campuses to request assistance to collect data from the sample group. A total of 200 questionnaires were returned, representing 100%.

12. Data Analysis

The researcher used a statistical package to analyze the data, which includes the following details:

1. The correlation was analyzed between student factors, English language instructor factors and environment factors and students' achievement in English language learning at Thailand National Sports University of Central Region, using Pearson correlation coefficient analysis.
2. An analysis of student factors in English language instructors and environment and students' achievement in English language learning at the Thailand National Sports University of Central Region by using Stepwise Multiple Regression Analysis.

13. Data analysis results

1. The results of the analysis of the relationship between student factors, English language instructor factors and environment factors and achievement in English language learning.
2. Analysis of factors affecting achievement in English language learning.

Table 1: The correlation coefficient between various factors and learning achievement in English for Communication Studies.

	X ₁	X ₂	X ₃	X ₄	X ₅	X ₆	X ₇	X ₈	Y
X ₁	1.00								
X ₂	.743**	1.00							
X ₃	.706**	.786**	1.00						
X ₄	.669**	.744**	.800**	1.00					
X ₅	.599**	.650**	.691**	.689**	1.00				
X ₆	.469**	.547**	.580**	.563**	.536**	1.00			
X ₇	.609**	.730**	.741**	.727**	.623**	.565**	1.00		
X ₈	.502**	.663**	.676**	.601**	.564**	.465**	.275**	1.00	
Y	.525**	.591**	.211**	.564**	.436**	.430**	.651**	.237**	1.00

** p<.01

From Table 1, the results of the analysis of multiple correlation coefficients between various factors and learning achievement in English for Communication Studies showed that all factors (X₁-X₈) were related to learning achievement in English for Communication Course (Y) with a statistically significant level of .01 with a correlation coefficient between .211 - .651.

Table 2: Factors Affecting Learning Achievement in English for Communication (independent variable).

Independent variable	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	sig
a (Constant)	1.125			6.414	.000
X ₁	.320	.075	.375	4.747	.000
X ₄	.139	.057	.165	3.545	.000
X ₂	.124	.064	.135	3.728	.000
X ₇	.096	.046	.128	1.458	.000

R = .730 R Square = .532 Adjusted R Square = .525 F= 76.793**

From Table 2, it was found that the factors affecting students' achievement in English language learning at the Thailand National Sports University of Central Region were statistically significant at the .01 level including 4 variables, sorted by the predictive coefficient from descending as follows: attitude variables towards learning English language course (X₁), instruction management variable (X₄), student availability variable (X₂), and classroom environment variable (X₇). The four factors together explained the variance of students' achievement in English language learning at Thailand National Sports University of Central Region by 52.50% and could be used to forecast the Achievement in English language learning at the central sports university students in the form of raw scores and standard scores as follows:

$$Y = 1.125 + .320 X_1 + .139 X_4 + .124 X_2 + .096 X_7$$

$$Z = .375 z_1 + .165 z_4 + .135 z_2 + .128 z_7$$

14. Summary of research results

1. Student factors, English language instructor factors and environment factors, were positively correlated with students' achievement in English language learning at Thailand National Sports University of Central Region at statistically significant level of 01.
2. There were 4 factors affecting the students' achievement in English language learning at the Thailand National Sports University of Central Region were statistically significant at the .01 level sorted by the predictive coefficient from descending as follows: attitude variables towards learning English language course (X_1), instruction management variable (X_4), student availability variable (X_2), and classroom environment variable (X_7). The four factors could jointly explain the variance of students' achievement in English language learning at Thailand National Sports University of Central Region by 52.50%.

15. Discussion

From the research results, it was found that there were variables of 3 factors, namely student factors, English language instructor factors and environment factors, which significantly affected the learning achievement in English for Communication at the .01 level, which was based on the research hypothesis. The results were discussed as follows:

Student factors affecting learning achievement in English for Communication course consisted of 2 variables, namely the variable of attitude towards learning English (X_1) and student readiness (X_2). The variables in student attitudes affecting achievement in English language learning may be due to the fact that attitudes are important and influencing learners' language proficiency and language learning success (Reid, 2003; Visser, 2008) and Padwick (2010), who said that the nature of language learning lies in the learner's motivation and attitude towards language learning. This is in line with the research results of Gardner and Lambert (1972: 1-136) found that influencing factors in English language learning were attitude towards instructors, attitude towards the content of the course, and in line with the research results of Aimatchara Khotkaew, et al (2011: Abstract) who studied the factors affecting the learning achievement of students in the category of Business Administration at the Higher Vocational College level, Northeastern Vocational College. The results showed that the factors affecting the learning achievement of students with a statistical significance at the 0.05 level were the student's attitude towards learning. It was able to explain the variance of the student's learning achievement by 28 percent with a statistical significance at the 0.05 level. It is also in accordance with the research results of Nuchanat Vorayossri (2001: 50) studied the factors related to the students' achievement in English language learning at Rajamangala Institute of Technology, South Bangkok Campus. It was found that the relationship between student factors, social factors and teaching and learning factors and students' achievement in English language learning had a statistically significant positive correlation at the 0.05 level, and it was found that the variables that could predict the outcomes of Achievement in English language learning were: attitude towards learning English, in which the variance could be explained by 21.80% with a statistical significance level of .01.

As for the student readiness variable that affects achievement in English language learning, it may be because learners who are ready to learn English must be students who have planned, scheduling, arrangements, equipment, allocated time for studying the lesson in advance, reviewed the lesson before studying, doing more research to understand the lesson better This includes watching movies in English with subtitles, listening to their favorite international songs and studying the lyrics to find the meaning of words and expressions in the songs, playing games where students can practice English, and always converse with foreigners who speak English whenever the opportunity arises. Such students' preparation for study will result in better achievement in English language learning, in line with Cronbach's (Cronbach, 1954) concept that readiness of learners is an essential element of learning. If learners have prepared both body and mind, the learning materials and the environment are ready before the class, they will make the learning achievement at a good level. Therefore, the development of learning achievement must prepare learners to be ready to learn. Learners are very important in learning. No matter how good the instructor has the knowledge transfer, if the learners are not ready, don't care, don't pay attention, learning

will not happen. On the other hand, if the learners are ready to learn physically, mentally, with interest and attention, they will lead to learning as well which will result in better learning achievement too.

English language instructor factors affecting achievement in English language learning were 2 variables for English language instructors' learning achievement in English language instructors, namely the learning and teaching management variable (X_4). Teaching management that affects achievement in English language learning may be due to the fact that instructors are well prepared to teach, which has a positive effect on students' academic performance. This is because if the instructor can prepare the teaching to teach on time, prepare various appropriate materials and attract the attention of students, review the original content before teaching in order to organize teaching activities in accordance with the new content, give examples for explanations, suggest sources to find knowledge and always have questions to measure the understanding of the students during the course, they will result in the students' knowledge and understanding of learning more, which is consistent with the teaching management model of Bronfenbrenner (Bronfenbrenner, 1977) who found that instructors influence teaching and learning in many ways, especially instructional management, teaching preparation and teaching processes that affect learners' learning achievements, study related to the course taught until able to clearly explain the content of the course taught, with examples to illustrate, explain and answer questions about the course taught in detail, explain the course taught and link them to other courses so that learners can gain knowledge, understanding, as well as summarize important content after teaching and assigning tasks for students to review appropriately, resulting in better learning achievements in English course.

As for the environment factors, from the research findings that the classroom environment variables affect the students' achievement in English language learning. This may be because the classroom environment should be well ventilated, not too hot, noise-free, clean, with the availability of educational materials which will affect the student's study intentions, making students have a good learning achievement. This is consistent with what Benson (Benson, 2007) who said that the classroom environment and atmosphere help learners to learn better. Therefore, teaching and learning in the classroom, the instructor must create an atmosphere and environment that will help learners to learn. From the classroom environment concept, according to the ecological environment model of Bronfenbrenner (Bronfenbrenner, 1977), there are three teaching and educational contexts including the classroom system, the school system, and the community system. Therefore, the classroom environment is the teaching context that is closest to the learner and the instructor, such as light, sound, color, air, classroom size, school supplies, etc. As Bronfenbrenner explained, the study of anything, especially living things, needs to be studied or taken into account in order to be successful in educational management, so the classroom environment affects learning achievement.

16. Suggestions for implementation

1. At the executive level involved in overall educational policy, such as at the executive level, at the university and at the campus level, emphasis should be placed on promoting and training English language instructors to be management experts to be able to provide good teaching and always have the opportunity to increase knowledge, abilities, especially encouraged to receive training and study visits in native-speaking countries.
2. The Faculty of Liberal Arts responsible for teaching English should provide students with preparation in addition to classroom instruction, such as organizing an English camp, organizing a training course on preparing the foundation for English language learning. This is because learners who are well prepared will result in better learning achievement.
3. English language instructors should always be prepared to teach. Appropriate media should be selected for students seeking additional knowledge in both teaching and learning management, and the study of teaching and learning psychology for the benefit of accessibility, understanding of the students, allowing instructors to choose and adjust the teaching and learning methods that are suitable for each group of students appropriately. This will help students to focus on their studies and ultimately achieve better English language learning.
4. Advisors should motivate and inspire students to recognize the importance of English language achievement as well as caring to provide students with help, advice on preparation, and academic preparation that will help them improve their achievement in English language learning.

17. Suggestions for future research

1. The causal factors affecting achievement in English language learning should be studied, which will provide a wide range of information that can be used to improve the quality of English language learning.
2. There should be an experimental research study in English language course management that is suitable and effective for physical education students.

References

- Aimatchara Kotkaew, Padungchai Phupat and Amnat Tangcharoenchai. (2011) Factors affecting the learning achievement of students in the category of Business Administration at the Higher Vocational Certificate level, Northeastern Vocational College. *Journal of Industrial Education*, 10(3), 246-254.
- Benson, P. (2007). Autonomy in language teaching and learning (State-of-the-Art article). *Language Teaching*, 40, 21–40.
- Bloom, Benjamin. (1976). *Human Characteristic and School Learning*. New York : McGraw-Hill Book Company.
- Bronfenbrenner, U. (1977). Toward an experimental ecology of human development. *American Psychologist*, 32(7), 513–531.
- Chatkaew Paowiset and Wanwipha Chatuchai. (2013) *Factors Affecting English Program Student Achievement*. Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, Suan Dusit Rajabhat University, Bangkok.
- Creemers, B.P.M. (1994). *The effective classroom*. London : Cassell.
- Cronbach, L. J. (1954). *Educational psychology*. New York : Harcourt.
- Gardner, R.C.& Lambert, W.E.(1972). Motivation Variables in Second Language Acquisition. In *Attitude and Motivation in Second Language Learning*, 40(1), 21-40.
- Nuchanart Vorayossri. (2001). *Factors related to students' achievement in English language learning at Rajamangala Institute of Technology, Southern Bangkok Campus*. Thesis M.Ed. (Higher Education). Graduate School, Srinakharinwirot University, Bangkok.
- Office of the Higher Education Commission. (2010). *Strategy of higher education in Thailand in preparation for Ready for the ASEAN Community in 2015*. Bangkok: Bangkok Blog.
- Paiboon Sukwijit (2010). *A Study of Factors Affecting the Achievement in Basic English of 2nd Year Students at Sripatum University*, Sripatum University, Bangkok.
- Padwick, A. (2010). *Attitudes towards English and Varieties of English in Globalizing India*. University of Groningen.Newcastle, England.
- Reid, N. (2003). *Getting started in pedagogical research in the physical science*. LTSN Physical Sciences Centre, University of Hull, University of Groningen.Newcastle, England.
- Visser, P.S, (2008). *Knowledge and Attitudes*. In Wonsbach & M.W.
- Wiley and Wrigley, G. (1987). *Communicating in the real world: Developing Communication Skills for Business and the Professions*. California State University, Long Beach. Prentice Hall Regents.
- Wilkins, D. K. (1974). *Second-language learning and teaching*. London : Edward Arnold.